

Procedure for increasing yellow stem borer resistance.

Origin and seed source of lines and varieties with moderate resistance to stem borers. IRRI, 1981.

Line or variety	Origin	Seed source
ARC10451	India	Acc. 20925
ARC12171	India	Acc. 21959
ARC12387	India	Acc. 22023
Aus Balam	Bangladesh	Acc. 25832
Biplab	Bangladesh	Acc. 26952
CO 18	India	Acc. 6331
CO 21	India	Acc. 6396
CR34-73-200	India	CRRI, Cuttack
CR94-13	India	CRRI, Cuttack
CR157-392-4	India	CRRI, Cuttack
Donangnouan	Laos	Acc. 29953
IARI 5829	India	Acc. 14423
IET5121	India	AICRIP, Hyderabad
IR18 20-52-2-4-1	Philippines	IRRI breeding line
IR3941-97-1	Philippines	IRRI breeding line
IR13639-34	Philippines	IRRI breeding line
IR13641-18	Philippines	IRRI breeding line
IR19362-183	Philippines	IRRI breeding line
Leggu	Philippines	Acc. 11261
Liberian Coll. Y-082	Liberia	Acc. 30848
MTU 15	India	Acc. 6365
Ratna	India	Acc. 12890
RP887-46-1	India	AICRIP, Hyderabad
TKM6	India	Acc. 6216
Warangal Culture 1253	India	Acc. 11055
Warangal Culture 1263	India	Acc. 11057

under normal condition without protection.

At maturity, plants are selected for desired characteristics, making sure that a number of male sterile plants are included.

The bulk seed of the selected plants is grown at hot spots as in an earlier season and artificially reared stem borers are released to provide pest pressure. At maturity, resistant plants free of dead-hearts and whiteheads are selected.

This selection for elevated level of resistance is done for three cycles.

Finally, fertile plants of the desired phenotype are grown in the pedigree nursery.

To select more resistant lines, stem borer pressure may be increased either by growing at hot spots or by hand-infesting plants with first-instar larvae reared from egg masses collected in the field. Seeds from other such developed populations also can be added at any step. This process may continue as long as desired, but fully fertile and resistant segregants may be extracted and tested for level of resistance at desired agronomic bases. Step 10 and onwards may be handled by rapid generation advance system wherever facilities are available. ■

Varietal screening for resistance to brown planthopper and its biotype in Bangladesh

Md. Anwarul Kabir and M. S. Alam, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), GPO Box No. 911, Dacca, Bangladesh

The first brown planthopper (BPH) outbreak in Bangladesh occurred in 1976. Screening against the BPH and its biotype was done in the greenhouse at BRRI. Of 450 rices screened, only 10 were found highly resistant and 27 resistant (see table).

IRRI has reported that Mudgo is resistant to biotype 1 and ASD7 to biotype 2. In Bangladesh, both are susceptible. Ptb 33 was reported resistant in India but showed variable reaction in this screening.

From the differential reaction of Mudgo, ASD7, and Ptb 33 to BPH, it is

now clear that the biotype in Bangladesh is not biotype 1 or 2, but is either 3 or 4. ■

List of BPH-resistant materials. BRRI, 1980.

Variety or line	Origin	Reaction ^a to BPH
ARC6650	India	HR
ARC10550		HR
ARC14529		HR
Sinna Sivappu	Thailand	HR
BR.593-1-1-5	Bangladesh	HR
BR593-46-8-2-1		HR
BR593-46-8-2		HR
BR593-46-8-2-4		HR
IR19661-347	IRRI	HR
IR19661-372	IRRI	HR
BG367-9	Sri Lanka	R
BG379-1		R
BG379-3		R
BR593-1-1-2	Bangladesh	R
BR593-1-1-3		R
BR593-48-8-2-5-3		R
IR13240-10-1	IRRI	R
IR13240-39-3		R
IR13240-1-B		R
IR13240-6-3		R
IR13240-10-1		R
IR13240-83-1		R
IR13426-19-2		R
IR13427-60-1		R
1314632-31-3		R
IR14632-272		R
IR19660-121		R
IR19660-189		R
IR19660-53		R
IR19660-161		R
IR19660-253		R
IR19660-192		R
IR19660-315		R
IR19661-13		R
IR19661-163		R
IR19661-364		R
Hondarwala	Sri Lanka	R

^a HR = highly resistant, R = resistant.

induced salinity.

Three hills were grown in each pot. One set of pots was irrigated with saline water (NaCl + CaCl₂ in 4 to 1 ratio), bringing soil EC_e to around 8 mmho/cm. Another set was irrigated with good quality water (EC-0.95 mmho/cm). CCC at 2,000 ppm and BA at 10 ppm were applied to pot sets as foliar sprays twice between primordial initiation and panicle emergence. Each treatment was replicated three times. Grain yield data indicate significant differences due to variety, salinity level, and growth regulator (see table). Under unsprayed saline conditions, Getu, with a 37.5% reduction from normal conditions, yielded more than Madhu with a 70.2% reduction from normal. However,

the extent of reduction varied under salinity in combination with growth regulator. In Getu, the yield was reduced further (72.4%) with BA but increased slightly (31.7%) with CCC. On the other hand, Madhu showed marked response to growth regulators under salinity, with a 55.3% yield reduction under BA and a 36.2% reduction under CCC. The apparent increase in yield could be attributed to increased grains per panicle and reduced spikelet sterility.

The results suggest that care be exercised in selecting varieties as well as growth regulators for improving productivity under saline situation. Getu, a salt-tolerant variety, did not better its performance when supplemented with growth regulators. ■

Effect of growth regulators and salinity on grain yield and associated characteristics of 2 rice varieties. Karnataka, India, 1974 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (g/pot)		Productive tillers (no./ pot)		Grain (no. panicle)		Spikelet sterility (%)		1,000-grain wt (g)	
	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu
	Control normal	32.8	32.8	24.0	25.0	87	95	24.2	32.9	21.1
Control saline	19.9	9.5	20.7	16.0	69	61	34.6	35.8	17.5	15.3
BA normal	35.8	31.7	26.0	21.3	82	101	29.1	26.5	21.5	18.1
BA saline	8.8	13.6	16.3	17.3	41	74	46.2	31.0	15.3	14.1
CCC normal	27.8	31.4	18.7	22.0	83	100	28.9	30.1	21.5	18.2
CCC saline	22.0	28.9	19.3	18.7	73	83	29.3	32.3	20.0	14.1
Mean	23.0		20.4		79.1		31.7		17.9	
C.D. 5%										
Variety	1.4		ns		2.8		ns		0.5	
Salinity	1.4		1.5		2.8		1.6		0.5	
Growth regulator	1.7		ns		3.5		2.0		0.6	

^aBA = benzyl adenine. CCC = chloroethyl trimethyl ammonium chloride.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Varietal response to growth regulators under saline conditions

K. V. Janardhan, plant physiologist, Agricultural Research Station, Dharwad-580008, Karnataka, India

A pot culture study during the 1974 wet season evaluated the effects of two growth regulators, 2-chloroethyl trimethyl ammonium chloride (CCC) and benzyl adenine (BA), on grain yields of rice varieties Getu and Madhu under

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Effect of seedling age on total plant elongation and internode elongation of deepwater rice

H. A. Quayyum, scientific officer, A. R. Gomosta, principal scientific officer, and M. Z. Hoque, head, Plant Physiology Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca, Bangladesh

Five recommended deepwater rice varieties were grown in wooden screening boxes (30 × 30 × 24 cm) for 10, 20, 30, and 40 days. Seedlings were then submerged in 100-cm deep water in con-

crete tanks for 7 days. The boxes were adjusted so that leaf tips were about 50 cm below water level.

The internodes of all varieties elongated as early as 20 days, but plant elongation occurred as early as 10 days. The percentage increase in plant elongation had no positive relation with the total length of internodes produced. Total plant elongation decreased with seedling age, but the number of internodes and their total length increased. The greatest plant elongation was observed in 10-day-old seedlings and the